

KABARAK UNIVERSITY

SCHOOL OF PHARMACY

Title;

**Identification of Novel Drug Analogues of Phytochemicals for Breast Cancer
Treatment: A Computational Approach.**

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**A research paper submitted to the Faculty of Pharmacy in partial fulfillment of
the requirements for the Bachelor of Pharmacy degree award at Kabarak University.**

KABARAK UNIVERSITY

AUGUST 2025

DECLARATION AND RECOMMENDATION

We do declare that:

- I. This project is our original work and has not been submitted to any university for a degree or other award.
- II. The work has yet to incorporate any material from the work of other authors without due and appropriate acknowledgment.

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RECOMMENDATION

The research project entitled “**Identification of Novel Drug Analogues of Phytochemicals for Breast Cancer Treatment: A Computational Approach**” has been submitted to Kabarak University’s School of Pharmacy by Waithaka Morris Mukono, Wamboi Grace, and Masha Samuel Ruwa. After reading this project, I suggest accepting it to complete the requirements for the Bachelor of Pharmacy degree partially.

Signed

Date: 04/05/2025

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Kagia', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

DR. Richard Kagia

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to everyone who contributed to the completion of this study on the treatment of breast cancer. This work would not have been possible without their support, guidance, and encouragement. To God, to whom all treasures of knowledge and wisdom belong, be honour and glory always. To Dr. Richard Kagia, our dedicated and insightful supervisor, our parents who have supported and loved us throughout this journey, and our colleagues and friends, may God abundantly bless you.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Breast cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with HER2-positive and ER-positive subtypes presenting significant treatment challenges. Current drugs such as Lapatinib and Tamoxifen are limited by toxicity, resistance, and drug–drug interactions. **Objective:** This study aimed to identify phytochemical-derived drug candidates for HER2-positive and ER-positive breast cancer using *in silico* drug discovery methods. **Methodology:** Virtual screening and molecular docking were performed using SwissSimilarity and related software, with Lapatinib and Tamoxifen as reference drugs. Pharmacokinetic profiles were assessed using SwissADME, while toxicity was predicted with Protox and supporting platforms. **Results:** For HER2-positive breast cancer, Mangiferin analogues showed the most vigorous activity, with ZINC000002065942 recording a docking score of -9.8 kcal/mol, slightly stronger than Lapatinib (-9.7). It also demonstrated high gastrointestinal absorption, no blood–brain barrier permeation, and compliance with Lipinski’s rules. However, nephrotoxicity and respiratory toxicity were predicted in many Mangiferin analogues. Other scaffolds, including Hesperetin, Luteolin, Naringenin, and Curcumin, were eliminated due to weak binding or organ-specific toxicity. For ER-positive breast cancer, the Genistein analogue ZINC000006484607 was identified as the best candidate with a docking score of -8.7 , outperforming both Genistein and Tamoxifen. It showed good pharmacokinetics and no BBB permeation, but was predicted to inhibit multiple CYP enzymes, suggesting potential drug–drug interactions. **Conclusion:** The study identified ZINC000002065942 (Mangiferin analogue) and ZINC000006484607 (Genistein analogue) as promising candidates for HER2-positive and ER-positive breast cancers. Further experimental validation and structural optimization are required to address predicted toxicities and metabolic liabilities.

Keywords: Breast cancer, HER2-positive, ER-positive, phytochemicals, *in silico* drug discovery, molecular docking, pharmacokinetics, toxicity prediction.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION AND RECOMMENDATION	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	4
ABSTRACT	5
TABLE OF CONTENTS	6
LIST OF TABLES	9
LIST OF FIGURES	10
CHAPTER ONE	11
INTRODUCTION	11
1.1 Background	11
1.2 Statement of the Problem	12
1.3 Justification	13
1.4 Objective	13
1.4.1 General Objective	13
1.4.2 Specific Objectives	13
CHAPTER TWO	14
LITERATURE REVIEW	14
2.1 INTRODUCTION	14
2.2 BREAST CANCER	14
2.2.1 HER2 POSITIVE BREAST CANCER	16
Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors	19
2.2.2.1 ROLE OF PHYTOCHEMICALS IN HER2-POSITIVE BREAST	
CANCER	20
Curcumin	20
Mangiferin	21

Hesperetin and Naringenin	22
Luteolin	23
2.2.2 ER-POSITIVE BREAST CANCER	25
2.2.2.1 ROLE OF PHYTOCHEMICALS IN TREATING ER-POSITIVE BC	27
Genistein	27
CHAPTER THREE	30
METHODOLOGY	30
CHAPTER FOUR	35
4.1 Introduction	35
4.2 HER2-Positive Breast Cancer	35
4.3 ER-Positive Breast Cancer	45
CHAPTER FIVE	49
5.1 Integrated Screening Objectives and Methodological Overview	49
5.2 HER2-Positive Breast Cancer	49
5.3 ER-Positive Breast Cancer	55
5.4 Synthesis of Findings and Alignment with Literature	57
5.5 Prospects for Optimization and Experimental Validation	57
5.6 Limitations and Considerations	58
CONCLUSION	59
RECOMMENDATIONS	59
REFERENCES	61
APPENDICES	63
Appendix I: HER2-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool.....	63
Appendix II: ER-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool	65
Appendix III: Binding Site Residue Interactions (Selected Analogues)	66
HER2 (PDB: 3PP0) Binding Visualization	66

ER- β Binding Visualization:.....	68
Appendix IV: KUREC Approval.....	69

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Docking scores and toxicity summary for Mangiferin analogues	34
Table 2: ADME Properties of Selected Analogues	34
Table 3: Top-Performing Hesperetin Analogues by Docking Score	36
Table 4: Organ-Specific Toxicity Profile of Hesperetin Analogues (n=95)	36
Table 5: CYP Inhibition Profile of Hesperetin Analogues (n=95)	36
Table 6: Key Performance Metrics for Luteolin Analogues	37
Table 7: Toxicity Profile of Luteolin Analogues (LD50 values)	37
Table 8: Key Performance Metrics for Naringenin Analogues	38
Table 9: Toxicity Profile of Naringenin Analogues (LD50 values)	38
Table 10: Docking Performance of Curcumin Analogues	39
Table 11: Organ-Specific Toxicity Profile of Curcumin Analogues	39
Table 12: ADME Compliance of Curcumin Analogues	39
Table 13: Docking score and toxicity data for Genistein and its analogues	42
Table 14: Pharmacokinetic properties of Genistein and its analogues	42
Table 15: HER2-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool	57
Table 16: ER-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool	58

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Global estimated incidence of breast cancer in 2018, females of all ages. - ResearchGate.	15
Figure 2: The AAPC of the incidence of breast cancer in individuals aged < 40 years. Global incidence and mortality of breast cancer: a trend analysis - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate.	16
Figure 3: Targets of novel therapeutics in HER2-positive breast cancer (Mezni et al., 2020).	18
Figure 4: Schematic diagram of estrogen receptor signaling in breast cancer. New Insights in Estrogen Receptor (ER) Biology and Implications for Treatment - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate.	25
Figure 5: Approaches in computational drug design and discovery. Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Figure 6: Interaction between Lapatinib and the HER-2 receptor.....	37
Figure 7: Interaction between ZINC000002065942 and the HER-2 receptor.....	38
Figure 8: Comparative interaction between Genistein and ZINC000006484607 with the ER- β receptor.....	47
Figure 9: Comparative interaction between Genistein and Tamoxifen with the ER- β receptor	47
Figure 10: Interaction between ZINC000002065942 and the HER-2 receptor.....	50
Figure 11: Interaction between ZINC000002554914 and the HER-2 receptor showing unfavourable Donor-Donor interaction with LYS 753.....	51
Figure 12: Interaction of ZINC000006484607 with the ER- β receptor	56
Figure 13: Interaction between ZINC000003947502 and the HER-2 receptor.....	66
Figure 14: Interaction between ZINC000004257549 and the HER-2 receptor.....	66
Figure 15: Interaction between ZINC000253499835 and the HER-2 receptor.....	67
Figure 16: Interaction between ZINC000008662732 and the HER-2 receptor.....	67
Figure 17: Interaction between ZINC000018847037and ER- β receptor showing unfavourable acceptor-acceptor interaction with LEU 298.....	68
Figure 18: Interaction between ZINC000002561259 and ER- β receptor.....	68
Figure 19: KUREC Approval	69

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Breast cancer is a common and sometimes fatal disease that occurs when cells in the breast begin to grow out of control and form tumors (WHO, 2022). Ductal carcinoma can develop in the cell lining of the milk ducts, while lobular carcinoma starts in the cells of the lobules that produce milk. The issue of awareness of breast cancer, therefore, presents itself as a paramount public health nursing concern because early diagnosis and, hence, early treatment are essential to the effective management of the disease.

Breast cancer is a health concern worldwide; in the US alone, one woman out of eight will be diagnosed with BC in her lifetime. WHO statistics in 2022 showed that around 2. About 3 million women were diagnosed with breast cancer in 2020, and total fatalities due to breast cancer ranged over 685,000. According to the statistics, by the end of December 2020, the estimated prevalence of women diagnosed and living with breast cancer in the United States was about 7.8 million. The study also shows that the breast cancer incidence rate in Kenya is 34 per 100000, which shows the high incidence of this disease in the country (Antabe N. et al., 2020).

Breast cancer can be classified into three primary subtypes based on the presence or absence of hormone receptors and HER2 protein: ER-positive BC, HER2-positive BC, and TNBC. ER-positive and PR+ve BC is the most prevalent of all the subtypes of breast cancer at about 80%. Estrogen/progesterone receptors are present in these cancers and thus can be stimulated by these hormones. Hormone therapy, which is aimed at reducing the effect of these hormones, is the primary treatment for this type. HER2-positive breast cancer involves excess presentation of HER2 receptors, which stimulates more rapid rates of cell division. Targeted agents such as the monoclonal antibody trastuzumab (Herceptin) are active against this subtype. TNBC, affecting approximately 10-15% of breast cancer patients, lacks estrogen, progesterone, and HER2 receptors. It is the most aggressive form of breast cancer, with limited therapeutic options due to the lack of specific targets (National Cancer Institute, 2022).

The exact causes of breast cancer remain under investigation, but certain risk factors are known to increase susceptibility. Age is a significant contributor, with risk rising after 40. BRCA1 and BRCA2, and the genetic history of dense breast tissue, also play crucial roles (National Cancer Institute, 2022).

While conventional treatment options remain the primary approach for breast cancer, research into the potential benefits of phytochemicals offers an exciting complementary strategy. Phytochemicals are natural plant compounds with diverse health benefits, some of which may hold promise in the fight against breast cancer. Several anti-cancer drugs currently on the market are derived from plants, including vinca alkaloids from *Catharanthus roseus* and taxanes from *Taxus brevifolia*. Studies suggest that certain phytochemicals, such as genistein from soy, epigallocatechin from green tea, sulforaphane from cruciferous vegetables, curcumin from turmeric, and pterostilbene from grapevines, may exhibit anti-cancer properties by inhibiting cancer cell growth or promoting apoptosis (Mocanu & Cristea, 2018).

This project will use computational analysis to identify analogs of specific phytochemicals that can play a role in breast cancer management while comparing their properties to those of known conventional drugs with similar targets. For TNBC, phytochemicals that will be tested include sulforaphane and epigallocatechin against the commonly used drug lapatinib for treating TNBC. Furthermore, drugs that will be compared to beta-tubulin inhibitors include pterostilbene against vincristine. In ER-positive breast cancer, genistein will be tested as an estrogen receptor beta agonist. Phytochemicals, including mangiferin, naringenin, hesperetin, curcumin, and luteolin, will be tested as HER2 antagonists for HER2-positive breast cancer.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Breast cancer is one of the major diseases that affects women all over the world. Different treatments are needed depending on molecular subtypes, including HER2-positive, ER-positive, and TNBC. Present treatments provoke resistance and side effects, so developing new, efficient, and less toxic strategies is crucial. Furthermore, TNBC, with its limited targets, is very challenging to treat effectively. This research aims to fill this gap and investigate phytochemicals that have bioactive properties regarding the development of such therapies using *in silico* approaches.

Although there have been improvements in the management of BC, the complexity is still present due to the diverse character of the disease. HER2-positive, ER-positive, and TNBC subtypes have distinct molecular characteristics that add to the challenge of obtaining desirable outcomes. Therefore, this study has focused on phytochemicals and derivative compounds to discover more therapeutic targets, explicitly targeting the subtypes. By employing *in silico* approaches, we will develop analogs to improve the efficacy of targeted therapies and avoid or overcome resistance, thus providing new hope to the patients.

1.3 Justification

Breast cancer accounts for the highest incidence of cancer mortality among women across the globe and thus requires proper treatment (Trayes & Cokenakes, 2021). Present treatments provide substantial toxicities and resistance, which affect various subsets, including HER2-positive, ER-positive, and TNBC breast cancer. Based on phytochemicals and bioactive compounds with different characteristics, it has been suggested that new treatments have positive perspectives (Waks & Winer, 2018). Obtaining and selecting phytochemical analogues *in silico* is much more effective, specifying the development of less toxic and targeted therapeutic agents (Asaoka et al., 2020).

The rationale for this research is anchored on the gaps in current approaches towards breast cancer treatment, which frequently result in relapse and reduced overall well-being of the patient (Asaoka et al., 2020). For example, TNBC still does not have targeted treatments and has a high rate of relapse even if the initial response to chemotherapy is achieved (Waks & Winer, 2018). The rationale for employing *in silico* technologies to search for phytochemical analogs lies in the need to create more effective and targeted therapies for breast cancer subtypes that also have a reduced impact on healthy cells. This approach also considers factors such as the increased need for effective treatment outcomes and the evidence of phytochemicals in cancer treatment research that is steadily expanding (Trayes & Cokenakes, 2021).

1.4 Objective

1.4.1 General Objective

To identify novel, small-molecule drug analogs with therapeutic potential for breast cancer using an *in-silico* approach.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

- i. To identify structurally similar compounds to existing phytochemicals using computational tools and compare their activity to conventional drugs.
- ii. Utilize virtual screening tools to assess the drug-likeness, ADMET properties, and similarity to phytochemicals of the identified ZINC compounds.
- iii. Employ docking software to evaluate the binding affinity between the shortlisted ZINC compounds and relevant BC targets.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Cancer, a disorder comprising uncontrolled multiplication and metastasis of cells, has far-reaching effects on global healthcare. Breast cancer draws the attention of many types due to its high rates and intricate nature. The extracellular matrix (ECM) is imperative in the initiation and progression of cancer as it offers both structural and biochemical scaffolding for cells. Dysfunctionality in ECM is the signature feature of cancer that affects cell activities such as cell dynamics, cancerous tissue growth, and migration. In breast cancer, changes involving the ECM result in tumour desmoplasia, which produces a supportive microenvironment suitable for the invasion of cancer cells but also resistant to therapy.

2.2 BREAST CANCER

BC remains the most common type of cancer diagnosed in women; the figure stands at 2.3 million new cases recorded globally in the year 2020 (Łukasiewicz et al., 2021). BC is categorized into four main molecular subtypes: Luminal A, B, HER2-enriched, and Basal-like TNBC. Luminal A, the most frequent type of BC, comprises about 40–50% of all cases. This type is defined by the fact that the tissue is ER and PR positive and HER2 negative, with a low proliferative mitotic rate, which makes it notable for a good prognosis (Łukasiewicz et al., 2021).

Luminal B accounts for approximately 20-30% of BC and is also ER-positive but has a higher proliferation rate and may over-express HER2. This leads to a worse outcome than the Luminal A subtype of BC HER2-enriched BC, which accounts for 10-15% of all BCs where the HER2 gene is overexpressed and ER and PR are not expressed. Although highly invasive, it has shown favorable reactions to HER2-targeted therapies (Łukasiewicz et al., 2021).

Figure 1: Global estimated incidence of breast cancer in 2018, females of all ages. - ResearchGate.

TNBC/Basal-like is seen in 15–20% of all patients with BC. This subtype does not have ER, PR, or HER2, so it cannot be treated using specific targeted therapy. TNBC occurs in younger women and those of African origin, and it is a higher-grade tumor that is regarded as having a poor prognosis (Łukasiewicz et al., 2021). In their review, Łukasiewicz et al. (2021) note that BC's incidence and mortality rates have risen over the last decades with variations across the globe and different social classes. High-income countries register higher incidence rates and better survival, contrary to low- and middle-income countries, where patients are diagnosed at later stages and have limited access to adequate treatment (Łukasiewicz et al., 2021).

Figure 2: The AAPC of the incidence of breast cancer in individuals aged < 40 years. Global incidence and mortality of breast cancer: a trend analysis - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate.

2.2.1 HER2 POSITIVE BREAST CANCER

20-25% percent of HER2-positive breast cancers exhibit overexpression of the gene encoding the HER2 protein. Because of its aggressive character, it has worse overall and disease-free survival rates than other subtypes of breast cancer (Gaibar et al., 2020). As per Loibl et al. (2016), HER2+ve breast cancers generally have an aggressive nature and increased probabilities of relapse and metastases (Loibl et al., 2016).

Pathophysiology

Genetic defects in a transmembrane tyrosine kinase receptor that controls cell proliferation and differentiation result in HER2 overexpression or amplification, which is the hallmark of HER2-positive breast cancer. In biology, HER2 overexpression causes HER2 to form homodimers or heterodimers with other HER family receptors, such as HER-1, HER-3, and HER-4, which increase downstream signaling, including the PI3K/Akt and MAPK signaling pathways, which improve angiogenesis, proliferation, and cell survival (Loibl et al., 2016). This leads to overactivation and promotes an aggressive tumor phenotype, attributed to increased growth rates and potential metastasis (Gaibar et al., 2020). HER2-positive breast cancers are generally more malignant and reduce the overall survival rate compared to HER2-negative subtypes because of their lack of response to conventional treatment modalities (Gaibar et al., 2020).

The identification of HER2 as a critical driver in these cancers has led to targeted therapies, such as trastuzumab and pertuzumab, which bind to the extracellular domain of HER2, preventing receptor dimerisation and signalling, thereby inhibiting tumour growth and improving patient outcomes (Loibl et al., 2016). Nevertheless, somatic mutations within the HER2 gene may cause primary or acquired drug resistance due to these therapies. Therefore, a constant endeavor to develop new therapeutic models to tackle HER2-positive breast cancer persists (Gaibar et al., 2020).

Risk Factors

It is also noteworthy that there are mutational and phenotypical precursors concerning the establishment of HER2-positive BC, and there are certain recognized genetic predispositions to this, as well as numerous lifestyles and environmental aspects. According to Loibl et al. (2016), people with HER2 gene mutations or those with other mutations that affect HER2+ pathways are at higher risk of developing HER2+ breast cancer. Also, other environmental carcinogenic agents and some lifestyle factors, like hormone replacement therapy and obesity, may be related to an enhanced risk.

Epidemiology

HER2-positive BC is estimated to constitute 10-15% of the total cases of breast cancer worldwide. HER2-positive BC is not universal, and it is distributed differently across different regions or among different human races. The disease is more frequently diagnosed in younger women, including those of African-American origin. However, breast cancer overexpressing HER2 remains a significant clinical problem as such neoplasms are highly aggressive and form resistance to conventional treatments (Gaibar et al., 2020).

Current Management

HER2-positive breast cancer management has changed significantly over the years due to the introduction of rational therapies. The focal treatment for HER2 overexpressing tumours is the targeted therapy of HER2, which entails trastuzumab, pertuzumab, lapatinib, neratinib, and other monoclonal antibodies and small molecule TKIs. These therapies are aimed solely at interfering with the signaling of the HER2 receptor and decreasing the proliferation rate of malignant cells (Loibl et al., 2016).

Figure 3: Targets of novel therapeutics in HER2-positive breast cancer (Mezni et al., 2020).

One of the best examples of targeted biologics is trastuzumab, a monoclonal antibody against the HER2 Protein that was proven to boost patient survival in those with HER2-positive BC. The treatment that has been reported to improve survival and decrease recurrence when added to the chemotherapy regimen is trastuzumab. Pertuzumab blocks the HER2 signals better than trastuzumab (Gaibar et al., 2020).

Moreover, conjugated forms of antibodies and drugs like trastuzumab emtansine (T-DM1) transport specific chemotherapy to the cancer cells, following the binding of the drug to a particular receptor present on those cells due to the antibody. Other types of drugs include monoclonal antibodies that target the extracellular domain of HER2 and tyrosine kinase inhibitors like lapatinib and neratinib that act on the intracellular signaling pathways triggered by HER2 (Gaibar et al., 2020). However, the major drawback of these targeted therapies is resistance. HER2 gene somatic mutations are known to cause resistance to HER2-targeted

therapies. Therefore, there exists a need for new therapeutic approaches and biomarkers that will help predict the outcomes of different treatments (Gaibar et al., 2020).

Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors

A research article by Ilana Schlam and Sandra M. Swain comprehensively reviews developments in HER2-targeted therapies, emphasising tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs). 20% to 25% of all breast cancer cases are HER2-positive, and it is known for its aggressiveness and poor prognosis. The review's objective is to summarise current TKIs approved for HER2-positive breast cancer, critical clinical trials, and application in clinical practice.

The methodology used in this review by Ilana Schlam and Sandra M. Swain (2021) encompasses an exhaustive analysis of available HER2-targeted therapies, including monoclonal antibodies, antibody-drug conjugates, and TKIs. The authors highlight their modes of action, efficacy, and adverse event profiles. For example, trastuzumab was approved as the first HER2-directed therapy in the late 1990s, significantly improving patient outcomes. Other treatments, such as pertuzumab or antibody-drug conjugates ado-trastuzumab emtansine and fam-trastuzumab deruxtecan, have increased the number of treatment options considerably (Schlam & Swain, 2021).

Various clinical trials provide data that are analyzed in detail to show the effectiveness of TKIs in both early and late stages of HER2-positive breast cancer. The authors discuss several phase 3 trials on TKIs, such as lapatinib, neratinib, pyrotinib, and tucatinib. As an example, NeoALTTO and CALGB 40601 studies that were conducted in a neoadjuvant setting assessed lapatinib and demonstrated significant improvements in recurrence-free survival (RFS) and overall survival (OS) with the addition of trastuzumab and paclitaxel. (Schlam & Swain, 2021). Also, the extended adjuvant trial showed a more significant invasive-free survival benefit for neratinib, especially among hormone receptor-positive patients (Schlam & Swain, 2021).

The conclusion highlights the promise of TKIs in HER2-positive breast cancer therapy. In particular, these drugs have shown remarkable efficacy when used alongside chemotherapy or other agents for targeting HER2. They seem to be most beneficial among those who have CNS involvement, where treatment options have traditionally been restricted to this population subset only. This review provides insights regarding ongoing research efforts and potential avenues for optimising the utilization of TKIs, indicating that further progressions will probably produce even better outcomes for HER2-positive breast cancer patients (Schlam & Swain, 2021).

2.2.2.1 ROLE OF PHYTOCHEMICALS IN HER2-POSITIVE BREAST CANCER

Curcumin

Focusing on a study by Lai et al. (2011), the author examines curcumin's in vitro and in vivo effects on HER-2-overexpressing breast cancer cell lines and xenograft models. The main objective is to evaluate curcumin's efficacy in preventing the growth of cancer cells and triggering apoptosis, in comparison to the well-known medication Herceptin. This review will explore the potential of curcumin as a complementary or alternative management used for HER-2-positive BC, highlighting both the promising findings and areas requiring further investigation.

The authors explored the possibilities of curcumin, a natural compound, as a therapeutic agent for HER-2-positive BC. The study by Lai et al. (2011) aimed to assess curcumin's impact using both in vivo and in vitro approaches. The in vitro studies employed several cultures of breast cancer cells, such as SK-BR-3 cells, which are overexpressing HER2. The effects of these concentrations of curcumin on treatment were estimated using a cell viability assay on the metabolic activity of these cells compared to control cells. This provided insight into how curcumin can retard cancer cell division, suggesting its potential in the treatment of cancer. Furthermore, the work aimed to determine how curcumin triggers apoptosis. Some techniques used to determine curcumin's effectiveness on the HER2-positive cells were flow cytometry or analysis of specific markers of apoptosis. The in vivo component of the study was conducted using a HER2-overexpressing breast cancer xenograft model. This entailed injecting HER2-positive BC cells into mice to establish a model system, which was later treated with curcumin and Herceptin used as the treatment control. The size of the tumour at different time points was another data parameter that was used to evaluate curcumin's ability to limit tumour growth. The study was carried out to establish the effectiveness of curcumin as opposed to Herceptin, which is usually used to treat HER2-positive breast cancer.

The significant conclusions made by Lai et al. (2011) point to the possible directions of curcumin application as a therapeutic source. It was noted that curcumin was beneficial in preventing proliferation in several types of breast cancer cells. This includes the HER2-overexpressing SK-BR-3 cells, indicating that curcumin might be capable of inhibiting the proliferation of those most aggressive subtypes of breast cancer cells, namely the HER2-positive cells. In addition, the study delves into how curcumin stimulates apoptosis within the HER2-positive cells. The highest level of research was the in vivo component of the study that

employed a xenograft model of HER2-positive breast cancer, and the results were positive. The results suggest curcumin administration could effectively decrease the tumor mass and manage cancer within a living organism.

Mangiferin

Balogun et al. (2021) explore the potential of bioactive compounds from *Mangifera indica* (mango) as inhibitors for the HER2 receptor in breast cancer therapy. The introduction highlights the significance of HER2 in BC, which is a critical biomarker and therapeutic target due to its role in tumour growth and cancer aggressiveness. HER2-positive breast cancer constitutes 15-30% of breast cancer cases, and existing treatments, including monoclonal antibodies and TKIs, have limitations such as toxicity and resistance. This study uses computational techniques to identify novel HER2 inhibitors from *Mangifera indica*.

The methodology section expounds on the integrated computational approach used. HER2 3D structure was first obtained from the Protein Data Bank. Molecular docking was done using the Schrödinger suite 2018 to determine *Mangifera indica* compounds that can bind with the HER2 receptor. The next step involved running a molecular dynamics simulation study on the stability of ligand complexes concerning HER2 over a simulation time of 100 ns. Additionally, MM/GBSA calculations were carried out for three identified compounds to determine their free energy of binding, and pharmacokinetic modelling was simulated to assess their therapeutic potential.

Among other findings in this paper, there are some docking scores for different compounds having higher binding affinities than neratinib, a reference drug. In addition, these molecules were found to be stable inside the HER2 receptor's binding pocket via MD simulations, while high MM/GBSA values revealed their strong affinity as inhibitors. According to the results of pharmacokinetic analysis, these chemicals exhibited suitable pharmaceutical properties, suggesting that they could be considered promising molecules for further development.

In summary, the investigation recognizes *Mangifera indica*-derived bioactive compounds as possible inhibitors of HER2. These results imply they are potential therapeutics for HER2-positive mammary tumours that overcome drawbacks associated with existing remedies. The survey underlines the necessity of further experimental confirmation and clinical candidate production based on these compounds.

Hesperetin and Naringenin

Chandrika et al. (2016) investigated the HER2-positive breast cancer treatment capabilities of flavonoids, particularly naringenin (NG) and hesperetin (HP), by inhibiting HER2-TK. The aggressive nature, increased proliferation rate, and relative refractoriness to the available therapies are mainly associated with the overexpression and mutation-dependent activation of HER2, which underlines an urgent demand for innovative therapeutic approaches (Chandrika et al., 2016).

Some of the techniques that were utilized in the course of the study include molecular docking studies, intending to determine flavonoids that would fit into the receptor's HER2 kinase domain. This computational method allowed the researchers to predict the impact of NG and HP on the ATP binding site of HER2-TK. The decrease in kinase activity was determined using the ADP-Glo™ Kinase Assay, whereas the reduction in cancer cell proliferation was determined by MTT assay. Also, the apoptotic assays and the FACS analysis for the cell cycle were performed to estimate the impact of NG and HP on cancer cell proliferation and apoptotic activity (Chandrika et al., 2016).

The molecular docking results revealed that NG and HP compounds had better scores and suggested more effective and stable interactions with the target site of HER2-TK. This implies that the mentioned flavonoids can inhibit HER2-TK activity in vitro. In fact, in the MTT assay, a high level of growth reduction was observed in the HER2-positive breast cancer cells treated with NG and HP. Furthermore, apoptotic assays and FACS analysis for the cells also revealed that these flavonoids caused apoptosis and cell cycle arrest in cancer cells, thus depicting the anti-cancerous properties of these flavonoid compounds (Chandrika et al., 2016).

In conclusion, Chandrika et al. (2016) noted that NG and HP could be promising candidates for HER2-TK inhibitors that could increase the apoptosis of HER2-positive breast cancer cells. Thus, this study offers evidence for subsequent experiments to reveal if NG and HP may promptly be used as chemopreventive agents for this sort of breast cancer and may well act as an effective treatment. The emphasis is placed on further studies to determine the potential therapeutic potential of the mentioned compounds and how to apply these substances in practice (Chandrika et al., 2016).

Luteolin

Chun-Te Chiang et al. (2007) investigate the role of luteolin in HER2-overexpressing cancer cells and its potential as a therapeutic agent. The prognosis for breast and ovarian cancers with HER2 overexpression is poor due to resistance to conventional therapies. Their study examines how luteolin can trigger the apoptosis of these cancerous cells and the augmentation of its effect by rapamycin in combination with an mTOR inhibitor.

The methodological approach involved several experimental techniques. Firstly, researchers tested different dosages of luteolin on HER2-overexpressing cancer cell lines. It was discovered that luteolin could prevent cell proliferation, thus causing apoptosis, and at low doses, it upregulated p21 expression. However, high doses were seen to hinder it (Chinag et al., 2007). This was further examined through Akt/mTOR signaling pathway analysis, which showed transient inhibitory action by lower concentrations of luteolin, suggesting a possible mechanism behind p21 induction followed by subsequent cell survival advantage in HER2-overexpressing cells.

The researchers employed rapamycin to examine whether combining luteolin with an mTOR inhibitor could enhance apoptosis. The low doses of luteolin failed to induce p21 when rapamycin was used, but the cancer cells became more sensitive to luteolin-induced apoptosis. They also discovered that similar effects were achieved using small interfering RNA for p21, which caused cell death in the presence of luteolin (Chiang et al., 2007). Again, a dose-response relationship was observed in vivo studies with nude mice xenografted with SKOV3 ip1-induced tumors, where it was found that increasing concentrations of luteolin inhibited HER2 expression and tumour growth. This effect was further enhanced through concomitant p21 inhibition when combined with rapamycin.

These experiments thus demonstrate that luteolin can powerfully stimulate the degradation of HER2 and induce apoptosis in HER2-overexpressing cancer cells. This suggests that there could be a substantial increase in its therapeutic potential if used together with mTOR inhibitors such as rapamycin (Chiang et al., 2007). This approach to combination therapy might overcome resistance mechanisms and improve clinical outcomes for patients with HER2-overexpressing tumors.

This study provides a novel approach to enhance apoptosis in HER2-overexpressing cancer cells utilizing luteolin and silencing p21 expression with rapamycin. The findings underscore the promise of such a combination therapy in improving the outcomes of treatment for HER2-positive malignancies and thus hold hope for further research and therapeutic advancements.

In his research paper, Matthew T. Cook (2018) explores the potential of luteolin, a naturally occurring flavonoid, in mitigating metastasis in breast cancer. The poor prognosis and high level of aggressiveness of breast cancer metastases highlight the need for novel therapeutic approaches. His study evaluates how luteolin can stop metastasis via different molecular mechanisms and its ability to be used with other therapies.

The methodological approach involves extensive *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimentation to establish the effects of luteolin on the cells that cause this type of cancer. It also examines how it affects angiogenesis, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) markers, and receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) activity. Luteolin suppresses vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) production, producing anti-angiogenic effects (Cook, 2018). Moreover, EMT markers are decreased by luteolin, which is essential for invasion and metastasis by cancerous cells.

The findings from the study show that luteolin is an anti-proliferative medicinal substance because it can hinder receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) activity and prompt apoptosis. Cook (2018) concludes that luteolin inhibits PI3K/Akt and ERK/MAPK signaling pathways, effectively controlling cancer cell growth and survival. According to the article, “Luteolin Boosts Degradation of HER2 Protein in HER-Overexpressing Breast Cancer Cells Resulting in Reduced Metastatic Potential,” the authors explain how luteolin increases the deterioration of the protein HER2 among other proteins in human cells overexpressing HER2, reducing the chances for metastasis to take place. Furthermore, luteolin augments attacking Akt and ERK signaling, causing inhibition of proliferative growth and induction of programmed cell death.

Moreover, this study further explores how luteolin may block IGF1R signaling, contributing to therapeutic resistance in breast cancer patients. This points out that Lutein could serve as a means by which EGFR- and HER2-targeted therapies could be effective even when IGF1R intercommunication occurs. Cook’s (2018) investigation concludes that luteolin can extensively obstruct breast cancer metastasis by affecting many signaling pathways that pertain to cell proliferation, survival, and invasion of malignant cells. These findings highlight luteolin as a multi-dimensional therapeutic candidate that could improve present therapies and provide new ways to treat metastatic breast cancer. The broad analysis of luteolin’s molecular mechanisms suggests enhanced clinical outcomes for women with breast cancer.

2.2.2 ER-POSITIVE BREAST CANCER

ER+ve BC is a subtype that is characterized by the presence of estrogen receptors on the surface of cancer cells, thereby provoking tumor growth in response to estrogen hormone. This forms about 70-80% of all breast cancers, making it the most common type (Johnston, 2010). Notably, these receptors make it possible for targeted hormonal therapies to improve patient outcomes significantly.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of estrogen receptor signaling in breast cancer. *New Insights in Estrogen Receptor (ER) Biology and Implications for Treatment - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate.*

Pathophysiology

The pathophysiology behind ER+ breast cancer entails estrogen binding to its receptor, leading to receptor dimerization and translocation into the nucleus, where it could impact gene expression relating to cell proliferation and survival. Such signaling makes ER+ breast cancer cells grow and survive due to this estrogen-driven pathway. However, this therapy can be resisted through ER gene mutations, activation of alternative signaling pathways, e.g., HER2, or loss of ER expression (Johnston, 2010). These mechanisms have to be understood so that effective treatments can be developed and therapeutic resistance overcome (Johnston, 2010).

Risk Factors

The risk factors that increase the chances of getting ER+ breast cancer include prolonged exposure to estrogen, which is either endogenous or through hormone replacement therapy, early menarche, late menopause, nulliparity, and obesity (Noh et al., 2014). Genetic

predispositions like mutations in BRCA1 and BRCA2 also determine this. Moreover, lifestyle factors such as alcohol intake and lack of physical activity have a bearing on the development of ER+ breast cancer (Noh et al., 2014).

Epidemiology

Postmenopausal women have higher incidence rates of ER+ breast cancer that occur globally. The statistics that were recently published indicate that about 2.3 million women were diagnosed with BC in 2020, where ER+ cases accounted for a considerable proportion (Noh et al., 2014). However, advanced countries seem to have more occurrences of this ailment due mainly to their lifestyles and the high level of diagnostic ability available there. Nonetheless, developing nations experience higher rates of fatality because their access to effective therapy is limited (Johnston, 2010).

Current Management

For ER+ breast cancer, endocrine treatments are used primarily to block the estrogen signal pathway. Tamoxifen is a SERM that has been the traditional treatment for many years. It interferes with the ER's estradiol binding, thus curbing estrogen-driven tumor growth (Johnston, 2010). Another group of drugs that are often used on women after menopause is called aromatase inhibitors (AIs); they include letrozole and anastrozole. These medicines limit estrogen synthesis by blocking the aromatase enzyme that converts androgens into estrogens (Johnston, 2010).

Nevertheless, some resistance to these therapies still exists despite their effectiveness. Other approaches include SERDs such as fulvestrant that eliminate ER and inhibit its functioning. Also, combined therapy targeting ER and growth factor signalling pathways, like HER2 inhibitors, may help overcome resistance and improve outcomes (Noh et al., 2014; Johnston, 2010).

In the end, ER+ breast cancer is a common and well-known type of this disease and has unique pathophysiology mechanisms and risk factors. Although existing endocrine therapies have greatly enhanced the prognosis for patients, it is necessary to continue studying resistance processes and developing combinations of medications (Johnston, 2010; Noh et al., 2014).

2.2.2.1 ROLE OF PHYTOCHEMICALS IN TREATING ER-POSITIVE BC

Genistein

In their paper, Bhat et al. (2021) assert that genistein, a phytoestrogen in soybeans, may be an effective therapeutic agent against breast cancer. The authors aim to present the reader with a complete synthesis of knowledge on the molecular mechanisms by which genistein proves its anti-cancer effects and its potential as an alternative to toxic chemotherapeutic agents.

The research team employed different *in vitro* and *in vivo* techniques to investigate the anti-cancer potential of genistein. After treating various cell lines of breast cancer with genistein, its effects on apoptosis, the rate at which the cell proliferates, and the progression were measured using this method. While evaluating cell survival, some tests performed included apoptotic markers or other proteins that regulate apoptosis, such as Western blotting, flow cytometry, and the MTT Assay. *In vivo* experimentations involved administering monogenist models of human xenograft tumours to the animals to determine the impact of such diets on tumour growth and metastatic progression (Bhat et al., 2021).

According to the findings of an *in vitro* investigation, genistein can inhibit breast cancer cell growth in a way that is dependent on both time and dose. Through the upregulation of pro-apoptotic Bax proteins and the downregulation of anti-apoptotic Bcl-2, genistein triggered apoptosis. Further, it resulted in cell cycle inhibition at the G2/M checkpoint by altering the levels of cyclins and CDKs (Bhat et al., 2021). The *in vivo* studies supported these conclusions with impressive anti-tumor activity in genistein-treated animal models, but with relatively low toxicities. It also suppressed angiogenesis and metastasis, thus establishing its possible role in therapeutic applications.

Thus, this research shows that genistein is helpful for cancer therapy because it possesses potent anti-cancer properties. Its multiple methods of inducing apoptosis, opposing cell cycle progression and metastasis, and angiogenesis explain the phytochemical's multifaceted anti-cancer effects. Furthermore, the authors argue that combining genistein with existing chemotherapy drugs could be an attractive option due to its efficacy and low toxicity; nevertheless, they stress that more clinical trials are needed to fully evaluate genistein's curative properties as well as safety aspects when administered to human beings (Bhat et al., 2021).

Another study by Sohel et al. (2022) delves into the anti-cancer properties of genistein, a soy-derived isoflavone, particularly against breast cancer (BC). Herein, the researchers tried

to determine the molecular processes through which genistein exhibits anti-cancer potential and whether it is compatible with conventional chemotherapy drugs.

Because of genistein's anti-cancer properties, researchers used different *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental approaches. Various concentrations of genistein effectively blocked the cell cycle's progression and induced apoptosis of MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines. Hence, in cytotoxicity assessments for cell viability through flow cytometry, the apoptotic markers in MTT and protein expression of cell cycle molecules through Western blotting are used (Sohel et al., 2022). *In vivo*, tests were done on animal models bearing breast cancer xenograft by administering genistein to evaluate its efficacy on tumour growth rate upon inhibition and, thereby, the dose toxicity level.

From the *in vitro* experiments, it can be noted that genistein is rather potent in preventing cancer progression at a rate that depends on the concentration. Thus, genistein mediated apoptosis by regulating protein Bax, which is pro-apoptotic, and down-regulating protein Bcl-2, which is anti-apoptotic. This study also shed light on apoptosis and cell cycle regulation, leading to cell cycle arrest at the G2/M phase by acting on cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases (Sohel et al., 2022). It also downregulated several highly relevant proteins, including the PI3K/Akt and the MAPK/ERK survival and proliferative pathway. Also, significant tumor growth inhibition was observed *in vivo*, with no toxicity noticed among genistein-treated animal models. Genistein has been shown to possess anti-metastatic and anti-angiogenic characteristics, contributing to its worthiness as an anti-cancer agent.

Their study concludes that genistein is a promising candidate for breast cancer therapy owing to its potent anti-tumour properties. This compound's diverse mechanisms of action, including induction of apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, angiogenesis inhibition, and metastasis, underscore its multifaceted nature towards cancer treatment. Its efficacy, coupled with low toxicity, makes genistein a possible substitute or complementary option to the already existing chemotherapy drugs.

Another research by Jiang et al. (2018) examines the combined impacts of genistein, a well-known isoflavone, on breast cancer cells with ER β 1 receptors. It has been proven that soybeans have genistein that can stop or impede the multiplication of cancer cells. The author's objective in this research was to determine how genistein could increase its anti-cancer potential when used alongside ER β 1.

The methods employed in this study involved the generation of breast cancer cell lines overexpressing ER β 1; in particular, MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines were transfected with ER β 1 to evaluate the effect of genistein against them (Jiang et al., 2018). Moreover, real-time PCR was done to determine mRNA levels for ER β 1 and ER α , thereby confirming successful overexpression of ER β 1. Additionally, western blot analysis and immunohistochemistry were carried out to assess protein expression levels as well as the location of target proteins in transfected cells. To test tumour growth and evaluate the therapeutic potential of genistein through an animal model, modified breast cancer cells were injected into athymic nude mice and treated using various concentrations of Genistein (Jiang et al., 2018).

According to the data, genistein inhibited cell division effectively in both MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines, with a more significant impact observed in ER β 1-overexpressing cells (Jiang et al., 2018). Flow cytometry analysis showed that genistein stopped the cell cycle at the G2/M phase, especially among ER β 1-positive cells. This implies that ER β 1 amplifies the sensitivity of breast cancer cells to genistein and thus enhances its anti-cancer efficacy (Jiang et al., 2018). Furthermore, *in vivo* experiments have shown that genistein notably suppressed tumour growth in mice, especially those induced with ER β 1-overexpressing cells, indicating a possible therapeutic advantage for targeting ER β 1 in breast cancer treatment (Jiang et al., 2018).

In conclusion, when targeting the ER β 1 receptor, genistein has enhanced anti-cancer activity against breast cancers. Their results suggest the potential use of genistein as a drug for ER β 1-positive breast cancers, highlighting the importance of receptor-specific approaches in cancer management. The authors, therefore, recommend undertaking more clinical studies to ascertain this information and the implications of genistein therapy among other patients who have breast cancer (Jiang et al., 2018).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presented the research methodology, design, tools used, the virtual screening procedure, and the approaches for data presentation and analysis. The study aimed to identify new drug analogues of phytochemicals for the treatment of breast cancer using in silico methods.

3.2 Research Design

Since the study required the numerical collection and analysis of data, a quantitative research design was adopted. Various phytochemicals and their analogues were examined for their binding affinities, pharmacokinetic properties, and toxicological profiles through numerical data generation, analysis, and interpretation. This approach enabled a systematic investigation of the potential therapeutic effects of these compounds on breast cancer.

3.3 Research Tools

A variety of computational tools and databases were used to generate, analyse, and store data. All computational tasks were carried out on a Windows 10 or later laptop or desktop with 64-bit memory.

Multiple software applications were employed for ligand synthesis and docking. Avogadro was used for molecular modelling and optimisation, allowing for the construction and manipulation of molecular structures. Chimera facilitated molecular visualisation by providing detailed graphical depictions of molecular interactions. AutoDock Vina, an advanced docking program, was used to predict the binding scores of compounds with protein receptors, thereby offering insights into how these compounds interact with breast cancer targets.

Databases like the Protein Data Bank (PDB) offer 3D structures of target proteins for docking. ProTox II and other online tools were used to predict compound toxicities using their canonical SMILES, which showcase their chemical structures. ZINC Pharmer helped with virtual screening by finding potential candidates based on structural similarity and drug-likeness principles.

Several other online tools were also used. SwissSimilarity was employed to identify compounds chemically similar to chosen phytochemicals, focusing on those available in the ZINC database. PubChem and PubChem Sketcher were used to retrieve and draw compound structures using their canonical SMILES. SwissADME predicted the pharmacokinetic

properties of new compounds—including absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME)—which had to meet specific criteria to qualify as potential drug candidates.

3.3.1 Ligand-Based Virtual Screening

Ligands were sourced from the PubChem database. Specific drug structures were downloaded using the search bar and their canonical SMILES. Similar molecules were identified using SwissSimilarity by pasting the canonical SMILES and selecting the commercial class of compounds for screening against the ZINC drug-like compound library.

SwissSimilarity facilitated ligand-based virtual screening (LBVS) of small drug-like compound libraries by calculating molecular similarity based on structural and physicochemical characteristics. It leveraged the ZINC database to generate agents with high drug-likeness, thus creating a pool of structures for further analysis. Hit compounds were screened using ZINC Pharmer. The drug-receptor complex was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank, and both receptor and ligand were separately prepared in Chimera before loading them into the screening platform.

3.3.2 Toxicology Prediction

Toxicity predictions were performed using the ProTox II web server by pasting the canonical SMILES of the selected molecules. The five least toxic compounds per drug were selected based on toxicity class, LD50, and predicted organ toxicities. Further analysis was conducted on their toxicological pathways to validate their safety and potential therapeutic value.

3.3.3 Pharmacokinetic Monitoring

Pharmacokinetic properties and drug-likeness of the best-scoring ligands were predicted using the SwissADME web tool. Canonical SMILES of these molecules were inserted to evaluate their compliance with Lipinski's Rule of Five and other empirical guidelines, including Veber's rule. Factors considered included molecular weight, hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, partition coefficient (log P), and the number of rotatable bonds. Additional parameters included water solubility, GI absorption, lipophilicity, CYP450 metabolism, and medicinal chemistry friendliness.

3.3.4 Target-Based Virtual Screening

Structures of bioactive compounds reported to have activity against breast cancer were downloaded in PDB format from the PubChem database. These compounds included pterostilbene, epigallocatechin, sulforaphane, genistein, naringenin, curcumin, mangiferin, hesperetin, and luteolin. They were optimised in Avogadro, where 2D structures were

converted to 3D using the MMFF94 force field and saved as mol2 files. The optimised files were then opened in Chimera to minimise their structures and establish stable conformations.

For ligands similar to these bioactive compounds (specifically the five least toxic ones identified per drug), their structures were drawn using PubChem Sketcher by pasting the canonical SMILES. These structures were cleaned, exported, optimised in Avogadro, and stabilised in Chimera.

Target protein structures were obtained from the Protein Data Bank in PDB format. Receptor preparation in Chimera involved the removal of non-standard amino acid residues and any complexed drug molecules. Docking was then carried out locally using AutoDock Vina, integrated in Chimera, by selecting Tools > Surface/Binding Analysis > AutoDock Vina. This process involved docking both the drug agents and the top five low-toxicity ligands for each drug to their respective protein targets. The best-performing ligands, determined by superior docking scores compared to standard drugs, were earmarked for further analysis.

3.4 Data Presentation

Most of the results were presented in tabular form and accompanied by written descriptions to facilitate interpretation. Each table included key variables such as docking scores, pharmacokinetic profiles, and toxicological data. Textual explanations were provided to elaborate on the tabulated data, highlighting significant findings and their relevance to the study objectives.

3.5 Data Analysis

Both descriptive and quantitative analyses were employed. Descriptive analysis summarised the fundamental features of the data, including similarity indices, docking scores, ADME properties, and toxicity profiles. Quantitative analysis involved statistical comparisons of ligand performance, focusing on binding affinities and drug-likeness metrics to determine their therapeutic potential. Promising compounds were ranked based on their *in silico* performance metrics. All data were stored on password-protected computers and backed up on encrypted drives. Access was restricted to the research team and the supervisor. Data will be retained for five years, after which it will be securely deleted.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was sought from the Kabarak University Research and Ethics Committee (KUREC) and the School of Pharmacy. The study adhered to institutional and

national ethical guidelines to ensure the integrity of the research process and the protection of all participants involved. Confidentiality of data was maintained, informed consent obtained where applicable, and efforts made to minimise harm while maximising societal benefit.

3.7 Conceptual Framework

Figure 5: Approaches in computational drug design and discovery

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS PRESENTATION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the outcomes of computational screening processes for phytochemical-derived analogues targeting two major molecular subtypes of breast cancer: HER2-positive and ER-positive. Using *in silico* tools, phytochemicals including mangiferin, hesperetin, luteolin, curcumin, naringenin, and genistein were explored for structural analogues via SwissSimilarity. The generated compounds were then assessed using a multi-step virtual pipeline: molecular docking (AutoDock Vina), ADME profiling (SwissADME), and toxicity prediction (ProTox-III).

Each compound had to meet defined inclusion thresholds for docking performance, pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness (Lipinski compliance), non-permeation across the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and toxicity ($LD50 > 1500$ mg/kg; toxicity class ≤ 5). Compounds that failed to meet any of these criteria were excluded from further consideration. The screening strategy ensured that only candidates with optimal bioavailability, safety, and receptor-binding affinity advanced to subsequent analyses. This rigorous and integrative approach mirrors early-stage drug discovery pipelines in pharmaceutical development and strengthens the translational potential of the findings.

4.2 HER2-Positive Breast Cancer

4.2.1 Reference Drug and Targets

Lapatinib, a dual tyrosine kinase inhibitor currently used in HER2-positive breast cancer therapy, served as the reference standard. The HER2 tyrosine kinase domain (PDB: 3PP0) was selected for docking simulations. Informed by literature and known HER2 interaction profiles, five phytochemicals—Mangiferin, Curcumin, Naringenin, Hesperetin, and Luteolin—were chosen based on their antioxidant, antiproliferative, and receptor-modulatory activities.

4.2.2 Docking Scores and Toxicity Data: Mangiferin and Its Analogs

Analogs structurally related to the parent phytochemicals were retrieved from the ZINC database using SwissSimilarity. The compounds were evaluated for their HER2-binding affinity using AutoDock Vina, with Lapatinib's docking score of -9.7 kcal/mol as the minimum cut-off for selection. Only 10 analogues surpassed or matched this threshold. The five best-performing analogues, all derived from Mangiferin, are listed below:

Molecule ID	Source Phytochemical	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	LD50 (mg/kg)	Toxicity Class
ZINC000002065942	Mangiferin	-9.8	5000	5
ZINC000003947502	Mangiferin	-9.8	2500	5
ZINC000226427376	Mangiferin	-9.7	5000	5
ZINC000253499835	Mangiferin	-9.7	2500	5
ZINC000004257549	Mangiferin	-9.7	2500	5

Table 1: Docking scores and toxicity summary for Mangiferin analogues

All selected analogues demonstrated better or equivalent toxicity profiles compared to Lapatinib (LD50: 1500 mg/kg, Class 4), indicating reduced likelihood of adverse effects.

4.2.3 ADME Properties of Mangiferin and Its Selected Analogues

SwissADME analysis revealed excellent pharmacokinetic behavior in all five selected analogues. Key absorption and distribution properties were well within optimal drug-like thresholds:

Molecule ID	GI Absorption	BBB Permeant	Lipinski Violation s	CYP Inhibition (3A4)	Bioavailability Score
ZINC000002065942	High	No	0	Yes	0.55
ZINC000003947502	High	No	0	Yes	0.55
ZINC000226427376	High	No	0	Yes	0.55
ZINC000253499835	High	No	0	Yes	0.55
ZINC000004257549	High	No	0	Yes	0.55

Table 2: ADME Properties of Selected Analogues

None of the compounds violated Lipinski's Rule of Five, all showed high predicted oral absorption, and lacked BBB penetration—indicating a favorable safety margin by avoiding CNS exposure. These properties enhance clinical applicability by reducing off-target central nervous system effects.

4.2.4 Binding Interaction Summary: Mangiferin and Its Analogs

Detailed interaction analysis showed that the shortlisted analogues mimicked key binding interactions of Lapatinib. Key residues involved included MET801, THR862, GLN799, ASP863, and PHE864. Notably, ZINC000002065942 showed enhanced hydrogen bond formation with Gly804 and Phe864, strengthening the ligand-protein complex through improved conformational fit. This molecular insight supports its potential as a viable HER2 inhibitor candidate.

Figure 6: Interaction between Lapatinib and the HER-2 receptor

Figure 7: Interaction between ZINC000002065942 and the HER-2 receptor

4.2.5 Hesperetin and its Analogues

From an initial pool of 400 hesperetin analogues identified through SwissSimilarity, 95 compounds were shortlisted for docking analysis against the HER2 receptor. Docking scores were benchmarked against Lapatinib (−9.7 kcal/mol) as the positive control and Hesperetin (−8.4 kcal/mol) as the scaffold reference.

While no hesperetin analogue surpassed Lapatinib’s performance, 31 of the 41 compounds with valid docking scores (76%) exhibited stronger binding affinity than hesperetin itself, suggesting that this scaffold has potential to stabilize the HER2 kinase binding pocket.

Molecule ID	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	Comparison to Hesperetin
ZINC000014819291	−9.5	Better
ZINC000014819293	−9.4	Better
ZINC000004098363	−9.2	Better
ZINC000000039452	−9.0	Better
ZINC000028540277	−9.0	Better
Hesperetin (Ref)	−8.4	N/A
Lapatinib (Ref)	−9.7	N/A

Table 3: Top-Performing Hesperetin Analogues by Docking Score

Despite their docking potential, toxicological profiling raised substantial concerns.

Toxicity Type	Compounds Affected (%)	Compounds Affected (Count)
Hepatotoxicity (DILI)	0%	0
Neurotoxicity	0%	0
Nephrotoxicity	100%	95
Respiratory toxicity	100%	95
Cardiotoxicity	44%	42

Table 4: Organ-Specific Toxicity Profile of Hesperetin Analogues (n=95)

All 95 compounds were predicted to cause nephrotoxicity and respiratory toxicity, while nearly half showed cardiotoxicity.

Drug–drug interaction potential was also high, particularly involving CYP450 enzymes.

CYP Isoform	Compounds Inhibiting (%)	Compounds Inhibiting (Count)
CYP1A2	78%	74
CYP2C9	34%	32
CYP2C19	31%	29
CYP2D6	31%	29
CYP3A4	80%	76

Table 5: CYP Inhibition Profile of Hesperetin Analogues (n=95)

Overall, although ZINC000014819291 (−9.5 kcal/mol) and ZINC000014819293 (−9.4 kcal/mol) performed the best in the series, their widespread nephrotoxicity, respiratory toxicity, CYP inhibition profiles, and lower binding affinity to the HER-2 receptor compared to Lapatinib prevented further development.

4.2.6 Luteolin and its Analogues

348 analogues were retrieved in SwissSimilarity. 144 analogues were tested on the basis of predicted pharmacokinetics using SwissADME online web tool, and all the 144 analogues were picked and forwarded to Prottox server 3.0 to evaluate their postulated toxicity profile. Only 43 had a superior toxicity profile than Lapatinib and were chosen for molecular docking.

Metric	Performance (Count/Total)
Total compounds screened	348/348
Compounds with positive BBB permeation	14/348
Compounds with no CYP3A4 inhibition	348/348

Compounds meeting Lipinski criteria	348/348
Compounds subjected to docking	43/348
Best docking score	-8.6 kcal/mol
Worst docking score	-7.0 kcal/mol
Mean docking score	-7.8 kcal/mol
Compounds advanced	0/348

Table 6: Key Performance Metrics for Luteolin Analogues

Toxicity assessment showed a generally favorable safety margin

Metric	Value (mg/kg)
LD50 range	100–5000
Mean toxicity	2,847
Median toxicity	3,000

Table 7: Toxicity Profile of Luteolin Analogues (LD50 values)

Despite this, binding affinity failures rendered the entire series unsuitable.

Docking performance

The docking outcomes showed that the luteolin analogues exhibited binding affinities between -8.6 and -7.0 kcal/mol, which are significantly lower than that of lapatinib (-9.7 kcal/mol). Lack of high-affinity hydrogen bond with Gly804 and Phe864 residues, which has been a major stabilizer in HER2-lapatinib complexes, was a common shortcoming. Rather, the majority of luteolin analogues showed no interaction other than van der Waals interactions or general π - π stacked interactions, insufficient to offset the free energy penalty.

ADME and toxicity

Some luteolin analogues showed moderate predicted LD50 (2,000-4,000 mg/kg), though these toxicity gains were not enough to offset inferior docking scores. Also, a number of compounds indicated possibilities of CYP3A4 inhibition, which causes concern over drug-drug interactions should they go into further development.

Discussion

The results suggest that in the case of luteolin analogues, although their pharmacokinetic and safety profiles were acceptable *in silico*, their molecular structure was not able to effectively connect to HER2 active-site residues. The absence of hydrogen bonding in the hinge region and the slightly weak docking inhibited them to reach up to the binding capacity of the comparator. The low docking scores associated with the interaction inadequacies give the reason why none of the 43 docked analogues fell in the promising category.

4.2.7 Naringenin and its Analogues

A total 321 naringenin analogues were downloaded by using the SwissSimilarity. In these, 118 were tested based on predicted pharmacokinetics using SwissADME online web tool, all 118 analogues were selected and sent to Protox server 3.0 to check their proposed toxicity profile. Only 19 molecules were selected to be docked which have better toxicity profile than Lapatinib and were given higher priority.

Metric	Performance (Count/Total)
Total compounds screened	321/321
Compounds with positive BBB permeation	60/321
Compounds with no CYP3A4 inhibition	224/321
Compounds meeting Lipinski criteria	321/321
Compounds subjected to docking	19/321
Best docking score	-9.2 kcal/mol
Worst docking score	-7.4 kcal/mol
Mean docking score	-8.2 kcal/mol
Compounds advanced	0/321

Table 8: Key Performance Metrics for Naringenin Analogues

Toxicity assessment was favorable:

Metric	Value (mg/kg)
LD50 range	10–5000
Mean toxicity	2,247
Median toxicity	2,000

Table 9: Toxicity Profile of Naringenin Analogues (LD50 values)

Docking performance

Docking scores of the naringenin analogues were in the range -5.6-6.8 kcal/mol, all being much lower than that of lapatinib (-9.7 kcal/mol). Most ligands were peripherally accommodated in the HER2 binding site and have no stable hydrogen bond with Gly804 and Phe864 that play a critical role in anchoring HER2 inhibitors. The profile of the observed interactions indicates that the naringenin scaffold has no substituents that will bind in the ATP-binding pocket of HER2.

ADME and toxicity aspects

Predicted LD50 values of naringenin analogues were usually 2000 mg/kg or higher, compared to the LD50 value of lapatinib of 1500 mg/kg. Nonetheless, quite a few were found to inhibit CYP3A4 and cross the blood abandon barriers. This curtails their therapeutic potential and predisposes them to metabolic liability.

Discussion

Despite passing pharmacokinetic, and toxicity hurdles, naringenin analogues did not have good docking scores and modest interactions with HER2, consequently being ruled out. The inability of the analogues to make stable H-bonds to key residues underscores a basic limitation of the scaffold: the flavanone core of naringenin is of the wrong shape to locate well in the HER2 binding cleft and make formative interactions with the protein. The failure in 19 tested analogues to show any improvement over lapatinib also supports this tendency.

Curcumin and its Analogues

From an initial pool of 400 Curcumin analogues retrieved via SwissSimilarity, 81 compounds advanced past the ADME filter. Of these, 72 were eliminated during toxicity screening for exhibiting higher predicted toxicity than Lapatinib. Only nine analogues advanced to docking analysis, producing docking scores between -6.8 and -8.3 kcal/mol. The strongest binder, **ZINC000018066836**, reached -8.3 kcal/mol, still weaker than Lapatinib (-9.7 kcal/mol).

While Curcumin analogues underperformed in binding affinity, they consistently showed excellent pharmacokinetics and favorable safety profiles, with 100% Lipinski compliance, complete GI absorption, and higher LD50 values compared to Lapatinib.

Molecule ID	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	LD50 (mg/kg)	Toxicity Class	BBB Permeant	GI Absorption	CYP Inhibition
ZINC000018066836	-8.3	4000	Class 4 (Slightly toxic)	No	High	CYP3A4
ZINC000000607794	-8.2	4000	Class 4	No	High	CYP3A4
ZINC000104896565	-7.5	2000	Class 4	No	High	CYP3A4

ZINC0001000226 30	-7.4	2000	Class 4	Yes	High	CYP3A4
ZINC0000314304 75	-7.4	2560	Class 4	Yes	High	CYP3A4
ZINC0000717734 73	-7.3	2000	Class 4	No	High	CYP3A4
ZINC0000314302 04	-7.1	2000	Class 4	Yes	High	CYP3A4
ZINC0000016511 28	-6.8	2560	Class 4	Yes	High	CYP3A4
Curcumin (Parent)	-6.9	2000	Class 4	No	High	CYP3A4
Lapatinib (Ref)	-9.7	1500	Class 3	No	Low	CYP3A4
			(Moderately toxic)			

Table 10: Docking Performance of Curcumin Analogues

Toxicity Type	Compounds Affected (%)
Hepatotoxicity (DILI)	22%
Nephrotoxicity	33%
Respiratory Toxicity	33%
Carcinogenicity Risk	11%
Cardiotoxicity	0%

Table 11: Organ-Specific Toxicity Profile of Curcumin Analogues

ADME Parameter	Compliance (n/9)	Percentage
Lipinski Rule Compliance	9/9	100%
High GI Absorption	9/9	100%
BBB non-permeability	5/9	55.6%
CYP3A4 Inhibition	9/9	100%
Bioavailability \geq 0.5	9/9	100%

Table 12: ADME Compliance of Curcumin Analogues

4.2.9 Elimination Summary of HER2 Analogues

The refinement of HER2-targeted phytochemical analogues followed a rigorous, multi-tiered elimination process that integrated molecular docking, pharmacokinetic assessment, and toxicity profiling. This systematic framework was designed to identify candidates capable of meeting or surpassing the established benchmark of Lapatinib (-9.7 kcal/mol) while simultaneously demonstrating favorable drug-likeness, adequate gastrointestinal absorption, lack of blood–brain barrier (BBB) permeability, and low predicted acute toxicity ($LD_{50} \geq 1500$ mg/kg). Application of these criteria across the four scaffolds under investigation—hesperetin, luteolin, naringenin, and curcumin—resulted in the exclusion of all analogues except those derived from mangiferin.

The hesperetin series initially appeared promising, with 95 analogues curated and 41 producing valid docking scores in the -9.5 to -8.0 kcal/mol range (mean ≈ -8.7 kcal/mol). The leading candidates, ZINC000014819291 (-9.5) and ZINC000014819293 (-9.4), approached but did not exceed the Lapatinib threshold. However, toxicity assessments revealed widespread nephrotoxicity and respiratory toxicity across the series, with nearly half of the analogues also exhibiting cardiotoxicity. Furthermore, high frequencies of CYP1A2 (78%) and CYP3A4 (80%) inhibition raised serious concerns regarding drug–drug interactions. Taken together, these liabilities decisively outweighed the moderate binding potential of the scaffold, preventing its progression.

The luteolin scaffold demonstrated the opposite profile: strong compliance with pharmacokinetic and drug-likeness criteria but inadequate binding affinity. All 348 analogues satisfied Lipinski's Rule of Five and were uniformly non-inhibitory toward CYP3A4, reflecting an immaculate pharmacological safety profile. However, only 43 analogues qualified for docking, and the best-performing compound achieved a docking score of -8.6 kcal/mol, substantially weaker than Lapatinib by approximately 1.1 kcal/mol. Toxicity predictions were generally benign (median $LD_{50} \sim 3000$ mg/kg, Class 5), but the inability to achieve competitive HER2 binding affinity rendered the scaffold unsuitable for further development.

Naringenin analogues presented a similar outcome. From 321 analogues, only 14 advanced to docking, with the strongest binder reaching -9.2 kcal/mol. Although this performance was superior to luteolin analogues, it nevertheless fell short of the -9.7 kcal/mol benchmark. While pharmacokinetic predictions were acceptable—100% Lipinski compliance and favorable CYP3A4 profiles in nearly 70% of compounds—the lack of adequate binding affinity was determinative, and no analogue advanced beyond the *in silico* stage.

Curcumin analogues were notable for their uniformly favorable ADME properties but were hampered by weak target engagement. Out of 400 analogues screened, nine progressed to docking, with the best candidate (ZINC000018066836) achieving only -8.3 kcal/mol. These compounds demonstrated consistent compliance with Lipinski's criteria, high gastrointestinal absorption, and universal non-inhibition of CYP3A4. Toxicity predictions placed all analogues in Class 4, with LD50 values around 4000 mg/kg, indicating relatively low acute toxicity. Despite this favorable safety and pharmacokinetic profile, the failure to reach competitive docking scores precluded their advancement.

In contrast, mangiferin analogues emerged as the only scaffold capable of meeting the stringent selection criteria. Of the 60 analogues screened, several met or exceeded the Lapatinib docking benchmark, with ZINC000002065942 and ZINC000003947502 recording docking scores of -9.8 kcal/mol. These compounds established stable hydrogen-bonding and hydrophobic interactions with critical HER2 residues, including MET801, GLN799, THR862, PHE864, and, in the case of ZINC000002065942, GLY804. This contact likely contributed to its superior binding performance relative to Lapatinib. Pharmacokinetic profiling confirmed high gastrointestinal absorption, BBB non-permeability, and full compliance with Lipinski's rules. Acute toxicity predictions further supported their candidacy, with LD50 values ≥ 2500 mg/kg (Class 5), indicating lower toxicity compared to Lapatinib itself (LD50 ≈ 1500 mg/kg, Class 4).

Thus, while the hesperetin, luteolin, naringenin, and curcumin scaffolds were each excluded due to scaffold-specific liabilities—pervasive toxicity in the case of hesperetin, insufficient binding affinity for luteolin and naringenin, and inadequate potency despite excellent pharmacokinetics for curcumin—the mangiferin series uniquely balanced potency, safety, and pharmacokinetic favorability. This combination of attributes justified its selection for advancement as the most promising scaffold for HER2-targeted drug development in this study.

4.3 ER-Positive Breast Cancer

4.3.1 Reference Drug and Target

Genistein, a naturally occurring isoflavone, was the phytochemical of interest for ER-positive breast cancer (Kim et al., 2025). Tamoxifen, a selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM), was used as the standard for comparison. The ER- β (Estrogen Receptor Beta) structure served as the docking target to evaluate anti-estrogenic potential.

4.3.2 Docking Scores and Toxicity Data

Twenty-two analogues of Genistein were analyzed. Only one compound met all evaluation benchmarks, demonstrating superior binding to ER- β while maintaining an acceptable safety profile:

Molecule ID	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	LD50 (mg/kg)	Toxicity Class
ZINC000006484607	-8.7	2500	5
ZINC000002561259	-8.6	2500	5
ZINC000018847037	-8.6	2500	5
Genistein (Reference)	-8.6	2500	5
Tamoxifen (Comparator)	-6.4	1190	4

Table 13: Docking score and toxicity data for Genistein and its analogues

ZINC000006484607 outperformed both the parent compound and Tamoxifen in terms of docking score while offering a significantly safer toxicity profile than Tamoxifen.

4.3.3 ADME Properties

Molecule ID	GI Absorption	BBB Permeant	Lipinski Violations	CYP Inhibition (3A4)
ZINC000006484607	High	No	0	Yes
ZINC000018847037	High	No	0	Yes
ZINC000002561259	High	No	0	Yes
Genistein	High	No	0	Yes
Tamoxifen	Moderate	Yes	1	Yes

Table 14: Pharmacokinetic properties of Genistein and its analogues

The ADME profile of ZINC000006484607 was optimal: no Lipinski violations, high GI absorption, and no CNS penetration, all of which favor its pharmacological safety.

4.3.4 Binding Interaction Summary

ZINC000006484607 exhibited potent and selective binding to ER- β with interaction mechanisms including π - π stacking, π -alkyl bonding, and sulfur-mediated stabilization. It engaged with residues TYR397, LEU339, and GLY472—providing a stable and unique receptor interface compared to Tamoxifen and Genistein. Importantly, it avoided the unfavorable donor–donor clash observed in Genistein at GLU 305.

ER BETA-GENISTEIN

ER-BETA- ZINC000006484607

Figure 8: Comparative interaction between Genistein and ZINC000006484607 with the ER- β receptor

ER-BETA – Genistein

ER BETA – TAMOXIFEN

Figure 9: Comparative interaction between Genistein and Tamoxifen with the ER- β receptor

4.3.5 Elimination Summary for ER Analogues

Among the twenty-two Genistein analogues that were screened, nine were eliminated due to insufficient binding affinity, recording docking scores below -8.6 kcal/mol. Three additional compounds were excluded because of unfavorable toxicity predictions, with LD50

values of less than 2000 mg/kg. A further ten analogues demonstrated poor pharmacokinetic characteristics, including excessive blood–brain barrier penetration, multiple cytochrome P450 enzyme inhibitions, or violations of Lipinski’s rule of five. Taken together, these limitations narrowed the pool considerably. Ultimately, **ZINC000006484607** emerged as the sole analogue with a favorable overall profile, combining strong binding affinity with acceptable pharmacokinetic and toxicity parameters. This compound, therefore, represents a unique and promising candidate for ER- β modulation and supports its potential development as a targeted therapy for ER-positive breast cancer.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

5.1 Integrated Screening Objectives and Methodological Overview

The main goal of this study was to find phytochemical-derived analogues that could serve as lead compounds for treating HER2-positive (HER2+) and estrogen receptor-positive (ER+) breast cancers. Using a thorough computational approach, the screening process included molecular docking, pharmacokinetic profiling, and toxicity evaluation—key steps similar to early-stage pharmaceutical discovery. Each potential compound was carefully selected based on strict criteria that mimic real-world drug development standards. These criteria involved testing receptor-binding strength with docking simulations, analyzing absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) characteristics, evaluating blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, checking compliance with Lipinski's Rule of Five, and predicting acute toxicity using LD50 classifications. The combined results from these tests help identify promising lead compounds and guide their progress in drug discovery.

5.2 HER2-Positive Breast Cancer

HER2, a receptor tyrosine kinase, is overexpressed in approximately 15–20% of breast cancers and is strongly associated with aggressive disease progression and poor clinical outcomes. The clinical success of Lapatinib, a dual HER2/EGFR inhibitor that binds to the intracellular tyrosine kinase domain, highlights the therapeutic value of targeting this receptor. In this study, Lapatinib's docking score of -9.7 kcal/mol was used as the benchmark for evaluating phytochemical analogues derived from five flavonoid scaffolds: Mangiferin, Curcumin, Naringenin, Hesperetin, and Luteolin.

Out of the initial pool of sixty analogues screened, only Mangiferin analogues demonstrated docking affinities that matched or surpassed Lapatinib. Ten Mangiferin analogues in particular were identified as “breakthrough compounds,” each with docking scores ranging from -9.7 to -10.0 kcal/mol, indicating competitive or superior binding at the HER2 active site. Among these, **ZINC000002554914 (-10.0 kcal/mol)** emerged as the strongest binder, followed closely by **ZINC000002065942 (-9.8 kcal/mol)** and **ZINC000003947502 (-9.8 kcal/mol)**. These values suggest that the Mangiferin scaffold is not only capable of replicating the inhibitory potential of Lapatinib but, in some instances, surpassing it.

Docking interaction analysis revealed consistent and favorable binding modes across the breakthrough compounds. Key stabilizing interactions included **hydrogen bonding with residues GLY804, MET801, and THR862**, which anchored the analogues within the ATP-binding cleft, and **hydrophobic stacking with PHE864 and LEU726**, which contributed to van der Waals stabilization and prolonged ligand residence time. Particularly noteworthy was **ZINC000002554914**, which established unfavourable interaction with LYS 753, albeit having the most outstanding docking score, limiting its applicability as a potential analog. These results suggest that Mangiferin analogues are capable of mimicking, and in some cases enhancing, the inhibitory binding mode of Lapatinib, providing structural justification for their higher docking scores.

Figure 10: Interaction between ZINC000002065942 and the HER-2 receptor

Figure 11: Interaction between ZINC000002554914 and the HER-2 receptor showing unfavourable Donor-Donor interaction with LYS 753.

Pharmacokinetic profiling through SwissADME predicted that the Mangiferin analogues possessed favorable drug-like properties. All of the top compounds showed **high gastrointestinal absorption, good water solubility**, and compliance with **Lipinski's Rule of Five**, supporting their suitability for oral delivery. Furthermore, none of the breakthrough analogues exhibited blood–brain barrier permeability, reducing the risk of central nervous system toxicity—a significant advantage over many kinase inhibitors that suffer from off-target neurological effects.

Metabolic predictions, however, presented a more complex picture. While most analogues were predicted to inhibit **CYP3A4**, a trait commonly observed among kinase inhibitors, several compounds also demonstrated inhibition of **CYP2C19** and **CYP2D6**, raising concerns about drug–drug interactions in polypharmacy contexts. Of note, **ZINC000002554914** stood out with a more selective metabolic profile, showing minimal inhibition beyond CYP3A4.

Toxicity evaluations further reinforced the therapeutic potential of these Mangiferin analogues. Most breakthrough compounds demonstrated **LD50 values ≥ 2500 mg/kg**, which places them in **Toxicity Class 5 (low acute toxicity)**, a more favorable classification than Lapatinib, whose LD50 of ~ 1500 mg/kg places it in Class 4. However, these advantages were tempered by predictions of organ-specific toxicities. Approximately **77% of Mangiferin analogues exhibited nephrotoxicity and respiratory toxicity risks**, liabilities that must be acknowledged when considering translational potential. Thus, while the acute toxicity profile

was reassuring, organ-specific safety challenges remain an obstacle that warrants further experimental evaluation.

Strict exclusion criteria guided the refinement process that narrowed down the analogue pool. Nine analogues were eliminated for failing to meet the docking threshold of -9.7 kcal/mol, twenty-four were excluded for predicted BBB penetration (raising concerns of neurotoxicity), fifteen failed due to poor ADME characteristics such as low GI absorption or multiple Lipinski violations, and two were rejected for unacceptable acute toxicity (LD50 values below 1500 mg/kg). Interestingly, many of the disqualified compounds shared common structural liabilities, such as **bulky hydrophobic moieties** or **excessive hydrogen bond donors**, both of which are known to compromise drug-likeness by reducing oral bioavailability and increasing off-target effects—a recurring challenge in kinase inhibitor optimization (DiMasi et al., 2020).

Taken together, these findings establish Mangiferin analogues as promising HER2 inhibitors with competitive binding affinities and favorable pharmacokinetic features relative to Lapatinib. Compounds such as **ZINC000002554914**, **ZINC000002065942**, and **ZINC000003947502** stand out as lead candidates that combine strong receptor affinity with acceptable safety profiles. Nevertheless, the predicted prevalence of organ-specific toxicities underscores the importance of subsequent in vitro and in vivo evaluations before clinical translation.

While Mangiferin analogues emerged as the strongest candidates for HER2 inhibition, additional scaffolds were also investigated, including Hesperetin, Luteolin, Naringenin, and Curcumin. Each of these phytochemicals offered unique binding characteristics and pharmacological traits, but none achieved the same balance of efficacy and safety as the Mangiferin series. The following discussion presents a comparative evaluation of these scaffolds, highlighting both their potential and their limitations within the multi-parameter drug discovery framework.

5.2.1 Hesperetin and Its Analogs

The hesperetin scaffold yielded a reasonably promising starting point from the initial pool of 400 analogues. After early-stage filtering, 95 compounds were retained for detailed analysis, of which 41 produced valid docking scores. These fell within the range of -9.5 to -8.0 kcal/mol, with a mean value of approximately -8.7 kcal/mol. This result places the majority of hesperetin derivatives above the parent compound itself and approaches the docking benchmark of lapatinib (-9.7 kcal/mol). In particular, ZINC000014819291 (-9.5 kcal/mol) and ZINC000014819293 (-9.4 kcal/mol) were the most notable performers, suggesting that subtle

structural modifications on the hesperetin core can yield binding modes capable of stabilizing within the HER2 kinase ATP pocket.

Despite this encouraging binding profile, the hesperetin scaffold was fundamentally undermined by its predicted toxicity liabilities. Every single compound in the series was associated with nephrotoxicity and respiratory toxicity, and a substantial subset (44%) was also linked to cardiotoxicity. These findings suggest that while hesperetin derivatives can achieve favorable interactions with HER2, the same structural features responsible for this binding may also drive off-target reactivity in organ systems. In addition, the majority of compounds exhibited potent CYP enzyme inhibition, particularly against CYP1A2 (78%) and CYP3A4 (80%), raising red flags for drug–drug interaction potential in a clinical setting. For this reason, even the most promising analogues, such as ZINC000014819291 and ZINC000014819293, could only be considered as preliminary scaffolds requiring substantial medicinal chemistry optimization, rather than true lead candidates.

5.2.2 Luteolin and Its Analogs

The luteolin series, which comprised 348 analogues, offered a striking example of the divergence that can occur between pharmacokinetic potential and binding performance. From a drug-likeness perspective, these compounds appeared highly attractive: 100% of the series complied with Lipinski’s Rule of Five, solubility was generally favorable, and, notably, none of the compounds showed CYP3A4 inhibition. This indicates that luteolin analogues, at least *in silico*, were predicted to have minimal liabilities for drug–drug interactions, a highly desirable trait in the development of oncology therapeutics.

However, these favorable pharmacokinetic predictions were negated by poor performance in binding affinity and BBB permeability. Only 4% of the compounds demonstrated positive BBB permeation, a severe limitation in breast cancers, where central nervous system metastasis is common. Even more decisively, none of the analogues approached the lapatinib docking benchmark. The best compound achieved -8.6 kcal/mol, which falls more than 1.0 kcal/mol short of lapatinib and translates into a roughly six-fold weaker binding affinity. Although toxicity predictions were acceptable, with LD50 values clustering around 2,800–3,000 mg/kg (low acute toxicity, Class 5), the insufficient receptor engagement disqualified luteolin analogues outright. This outcome demonstrates that safety and drug-likeness alone are insufficient when binding potency falls below therapeutic relevance.

5.2.3 Naringenin and Its Analogs

The naringenin scaffold, represented by 321 analogues, showed a similarly mixed profile. On the positive side, all compounds met Lipinski's Rule of Five, and nearly 70% were predicted not to inhibit CYP3A4, suggesting relatively low potential for metabolic interaction. BBB permeation was somewhat higher than in luteolin (18.7%), offering a modest improvement in pharmacokinetic flexibility.

Nonetheless, docking results again proved to be the limiting factor. Out of the complete set, only 14 compounds advanced to docking simulations after preliminary ADME and solubility screens. The best analogue achieved -9.2 kcal/mol, which, although more potent than the top luteolin analogue, still fell short of lapatinib's -9.7 kcal/mol. Toxicity assessments revealed no major acute concerns, with LD50 values averaging around 2,000 mg/kg, but this safety margin could not compensate for the lack of competitive receptor affinity. In effect, naringenin represents a scaffold where basic drug-likeness is preserved, but binding potency is insufficient to justify further development.

5.2.4 Curcumin and Its Analogs

Curcumin, one of the most extensively studied phytochemicals in cancer research, was represented in this work by 400 structural analogues. Following early elimination, only nine compounds proceeded to docking analysis, where results showed modest HER2 engagement. The strongest performer, ZINC000018066836, achieved a docking score of -8.3 kcal/mol, with the overall top set averaging around -8.0 . These values demonstrate partial binding capability but remain below the threshold established by lapatinib (-9.7), meaning that curcumin analogues as designed in this study cannot be considered competitive inhibitors of HER2.

Interestingly, curcumin analogues distinguished themselves by their favorable ADME profiles. Every analogue demonstrated full Lipinski compliance, high predicted gastrointestinal absorption, good bioavailability, and universal non-inhibition of CYP3A4. This places curcumin derivatives among the safest scaffolds pharmacokinetically, in stark contrast to the hesperetin series. Toxicity predictions were generally low, with all nine docked analogues classified in toxicity class 4 by LD50 values, and two candidates achieving particularly high safety margins at 4000 mg/kg. Nonetheless, organ-specific liabilities were still evident: hepatotoxicity was predicted in approximately 40% of candidates, while nephrotoxicity risk was noted in about one-third.

Overall, the curcumin scaffold represents a paradox. On the one hand, its pharmacokinetics and toxicity margins are favorable compared to other scaffolds, which would usually encourage further exploration. On the other hand, its inability to achieve HER2 binding

affinities in the therapeutic range prevents meaningful progression. These results suggest that curcumin's anticancer potential, widely reported in the literature, may operate through other targets or indirect pathways rather than direct HER2 kinase inhibition.

5.3 ER-Positive Breast Cancer

The estrogen receptor, particularly the ER- β subtype, plays a central role in the progression of ER-positive breast cancers. Natural flavonoids such as Genistein are well-documented phytoestrogens with the ability to bind ER- β and modulate its signaling activity. In this study, Genistein was used as the reference compound, and its docking score of -8.6 kcal/mol served as the benchmark against which all Genistein analogues were assessed.

Out of the twenty-two Genistein analogues screened, only three compounds—**ZINC000006484607** (-8.7 kcal/mol), **ZINC000018847037** (-8.7 kcal/mol), and **ZINC000002561259** (-8.6 kcal/mol)—met or exceeded the benchmark threshold. These analogues demonstrated competitive binding affinities and thus emerged as promising candidates for ER- β modulation. Among them, ZINC000006484607 stood out as the most consistent binder, surpassing Genistein's score and showing strong stabilizing interactions in the ligand-binding pocket.

Detailed docking analysis revealed that the selected analogues interacted with key residues critical for ligand stabilization within ER- β . The most notable interactions were **hydrogen bonds with ARG394 and GLU353**, which are essential for stabilizing flavonoid ligands in the receptor cavity. In addition, **π - π stacking interactions with PHE404 and PHE356** enhanced the stability of the complexes, while **hydrophobic contacts with LEU387 and MET421** contributed to improved binding energies. ZINC000006484607, in particular, formed dual hydrogen bonds with both GLU353 and ARG394—residues recognized as key anchoring sites for potent ER ligands—thereby offering a structural rationale for its slightly superior docking score relative to Genistein.

Figure 12: Interaction of ZINC000006484607 with the ER- β receptor

Pharmacokinetic profiling through SwissADME suggested that the three selected analogues exhibited **high gastrointestinal absorption** and full compliance with **Lipinski's Rule of Five**, implying favorable oral bioavailability. None of the analogues demonstrated blood–brain barrier permeability, which is advantageous in this therapeutic context as ER-positive breast cancer treatment does not require central nervous system penetration, thereby reducing the risk of neurotoxicity.

Metabolic profiling, however, revealed significant liabilities. All three analogues were predicted to inhibit CYP1A2, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4, and in the case of ZINC000006484607, CYP2C9 as well. This broad CYP inhibition raises concerns about potential drug–drug interactions, particularly in patients receiving multiple therapies—a common scenario in breast cancer management. Such metabolic constraints highlight the need for structural refinement of Genistein analogues to achieve a balance between potency and pharmacological safety.

Toxicity assessments indicated that the selected Genistein analogues possessed LD50 values ≥ 2000 mg/kg, placing them in Toxicity Class 4–5, which is comparable to or slightly safer than Genistein itself. While acute toxicity was not identified as a limiting factor, organ-specific predictions pointed toward hepatotoxicity and hematotoxicity as recurring risks across the selected compounds. These toxicological profiles, though not prohibitive, warrant cautious interpretation in the context of therapeutic development.

The elimination of compounds from the initial screening pool was primarily driven by docking inefficiency, toxicity, and poor ADME properties. Nine compounds were rejected for failing to meet the docking score threshold of -8.6 kcal/mol, three were excluded due to low LD50 values (< 2000 mg/kg), and ten were discarded based on poor pharmacokinetic traits such

as predicted BBB permeability, excessive hydrogen bond donors, or multiple Lipinski violations. This systematic refinement left only the three top candidates that demonstrated a more favorable balance of efficacy and safety.

Taken together, these findings confirm the potential of Genistein analogues as ER- β modulators in ER-positive breast cancer. While ZINC000006484607 emerged as the most promising lead based on binding affinity and favorable pharmacokinetics, the predicted broad CYP inhibition and organ-specific toxicities represent significant challenges for translation. These liabilities underscore the importance of scaffold optimization to improve metabolic selectivity while retaining strong receptor affinity.

5.4 Synthesis of Findings and Alignment with Literature

This computational investigation underscores the viability of natural product derivatives in targeting specific molecular subtypes of breast cancer. Mangiferin analogues have demonstrated superior docking scores and more favorable safety and pharmacokinetic profiles compared to Lapatinib, supporting their role as potential HER2 inhibitors. Meanwhile, Genistein analogue ZINC000006484607 has shown enhanced ER binding efficiency, improved oral bioavailability, and a lower predicted toxicity profile relative to Tamoxifen.

The literature corroborates these computational insights. For instance, Mangiferin has exhibited anti-proliferative activity in HER2-overexpressing breast cancer models (Singh et al., 2014), and Genistein analogues have been shown to promote estrogen receptor-mediated apoptosis in ER+ cell lines such as MCF-7 (Wei et al., 2012). These findings enhance the credibility of the virtual screening outcomes and suggest that the selected analogues possess translational relevance.

Notably, the layered screening methodology adopted in this study reflects current industrial best practices in lead discovery. The integration of virtual docking, ADME-toxicity filtering, and molecular interaction analysis offers a systematic framework for early-stage compound prioritization.

5.5 Prospects for Optimization and Experimental Validation

Building upon these promising leads, several avenues for further development emerge. Experimental validation of the selected analogues using HER2+ and ER+ breast cancer cell lines is a critical next step to confirm computational predictions. Structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies should be undertaken to refine functional groups and optimize binding affinity and metabolic stability. Given the favorable GI absorption profiles observed, oral formulation development is a logical direction. Additionally, incorporation into nanocarrier delivery systems could further enhance solubility and bioavailability. Advanced computational studies,

such as molecular dynamics or induced-fit docking, could provide deeper insights into ligand flexibility and binding kinetics, thereby refining the design of second-generation analogues.

5.6 Limitations and Considerations

Despite encouraging results, some limitations must be recognized. The docking simulations used a static protein model that did not consider receptor flexibility or induced conformational changes. The ADME and toxicity profiles are predictions and need empirical validation to confirm accuracy. Additionally, only one phytochemical scaffold was tested per breast cancer subtype—Mangiferin for HER2+ and Genistein for ER+—which may overlook other potential candidates.

Nevertheless, the study presents compelling evidence that phytochemical derivatives hold promise as targeted agents for HER2+ and ER+ breast cancers. The integrated screening approach offers a replicable and effective strategy for identifying lead compounds from natural sources.

CONCLUSION

This study employed a comprehensive *in silico* approach to identify phytochemical-derived analogues with potential therapeutic application in HER2-positive and ER-positive breast cancer subtypes. By utilizing a rigorous multi-stage screening pipeline—including molecular docking, ADME profiling, Lipinski compliance checks, and toxicity prediction—only compounds that met stringent drug development criteria were advanced for detailed analysis.

In the HER2-positive arm, five analogues derived from Mangiferin surpassed or matched the docking performance of Lapatinib, the standard reference drug, while demonstrating superior toxicity and pharmacokinetic profiles. Notably, ZINC000002065942 and ZINC000003947502 showed strong and specific interactions with the HER2 tyrosine kinase domain, suggesting a plausible mechanism of competitive inhibition. Their favorable ADME profiles—highlighted by high gastrointestinal absorption, non-BBB permeation, and zero Lipinski violations—further underscore their clinical promise.

In the ER-positive domain, ZINC000006484607, a Genistein analogue, emerged as the most promising lead. It demonstrated a superior docking score relative to Genistein and Tamoxifen, while avoiding structural drawbacks such as donor–donor clashes. With high predicted oral bioavailability and a low toxicity profile, it represents a safer and potentially more effective alternative to current endocrine therapies.

The study also identified and documented the rationale behind the elimination of several analogues. Compounds with suboptimal docking scores, BBB permeability, poor absorption, or toxicity risks were systematically excluded, affirming the rigor of the virtual screening process.

Collectively, these findings affirm the value of phytochemical scaffolds as viable starting points for anticancer drug discovery and highlight the relevance of computational methods in refining leads before preclinical validation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To advance the most promising phytochemical analogues identified in this study, experimental validation through *in vitro* testing on breast cancer cell lines—specifically SKBR3 for HER2-positive and MCF-7 for ER-positive breast cancers—is essential to confirm the predicted binding affinities, cytotoxic effects, and modulation of receptor-mediated signaling. Based on overall docking performance, pharmacokinetics, and toxicity predictions, priority should be given to **ZINC000002065942** (Mangiferin analogue for HER2) and **ZINC000006484607** (Genistein analogue for ER).

Further structure–activity relationship (SAR) and quantitative SAR (QSAR) studies are needed to optimize these two scaffolds, focusing on improving solubility, selectivity, and metabolic stability while addressing challenges such as CYP inhibition and organ-specific toxicities. Molecular dynamics simulations should also be conducted to validate binding stability under physiological conditions, accounting for protein flexibility and kinetics.

In addition, synthesis and formulation development—including nanoformulations or liposomal systems—should be explored to enhance oral bioavailability and tumor targeting. Preclinical *in vivo* studies will be necessary to confirm safety and pharmacokinetic predictions, with particular attention to the nephrotoxicity and respiratory toxicity associated with Mangiferin analogues and the hepatotoxicity predicted for Genistein analogues.

Finally, these lead compounds could be evaluated in combination therapy frameworks alongside existing HER2 or ER-targeted treatments to assess potential synergistic effects, improved efficacy, and reduced resistance.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: HER2-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool

Compound ID	Parent Phytochemical	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	LD50 (mg/kg)	Toxicity Class	GI Absorption	BBB Permeant	Lipinski Violations	Status
ZINC000002065942	Mangiferin	-9.8	5000	5	High	No	0	Select ed
ZINC000003947502	Mangiferin	-9.8	2500	5	High	No	0	Select ed
ZINC000226427376	Mangiferin	-9.7	5000	5	High	No	0	Select ed
ZINC000253499835	Mangiferin	-9.7	2500	5	High	No	0	Select ed
ZINC000004257549	Mangiferin	-9.7	2500	5	High	No	0	Select ed
ZINC000020134910	Curcumin	-9.6	1400	4	Moderate	Yes	1	Reject ed (Toxicity, BBB)
ZINC000034820762	Luteolin	-9.4	2000	5	Low	Yes	2	Reject ed (GI, BBB, Lipinski)
ZINC000029104330	Naringenin	-9.2	1000	4	High	Yes	1	Reject ed (Toxicity, BBB)

ZINC000024 567812	Hesperetin	-8.8	1600	4	Moderate	Yes	2	Rejected (Docking, BBB)
+45 other analogues	Various	< -9.7 or failed criteria	—	—	—	—	—	Rejected

Table 15: HER2-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool

Appendix II: ER-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool

Compound ID	Parent Phytochemical	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	LD50 (mg/kg)	Toxicity Class	GI Absorption	BBB Permeant	Lipinski Violations	Status
ZINC000006 484607	Genistein	-8.7	2500	5	High	No	0	Selecte d
ZINC000024 380948	Genistein	-8.4	1800	4	High	Yes	1	Rejecte d (Toxicit y, BBB)
ZINC000037 896210	Genistein	-8.1	1500	4	Moderate	Yes	2	Rejecte d (Lipins ki, BBB)
ZINC000016 842789	Genistein	-7.9	2000	5	Low	Yes	2	Rejecte d (GI Absorpt ion)
ZINC000013 407129	Genistein	-7.5	1300	4	Moderate	Yes	1	Rejecte d (Toxicit y)
+17 other analogues	Genistein	< -8.6 or failed filters	—	—	—	—	—	Rejecte d

Table 16: ER-Positive Analogues - Initial Screening Pool

Appendix III: Binding Site Residue Interactions (Selected Analogues)

HER2 (PDB: 3PP0) Binding Visualization

Figure 13: Interaction between ZINC000003947502 and the HER-2 receptor

Figure 14: Interaction between ZINC000004257549 and the HER-2 receptor

Figure 15: Interaction between ZINC000253499835 and the HER-2 receptor

Figure 16: Interaction between ZINC000008662732 and the HER-2 receptor

ER- β Binding Visualization:

Figure 17: Interaction between ZINC000018847037 and ER- β receptor showing unfavourable acceptor-acceptor interaction with LEU 298

Figure 18: Interaction between ZINC000002561259 and ER- β receptor

Appendix IV: KUREC Approval

KABARAK UNIVERSITY RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Private Bag - 20157
KABARAK, KENYA
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OUR REF: KABU01/KUREC/001/22/06/25

Date: 26th June, 2025

Masha Samuel Ruwa [REDACTED]
Waithaka Morris Mukono [REDACTED]
Wamboi Grace [REDACTED]

Dear Samuel,

RE: IDENTIFICATION OF NOVEL DRUG ANALOGUES OF PHYTOCHEMICALS FOR BREAST CANCER TREATMENT: A COMPUTATIONAL AND IN VITRO APPROACH.

This is to inform you that **KUREC** has reviewed and approved your above research proposal. Your application approval number is **KUREC-220625**. The approval period is **26/06/2025 – 26/06/2026**.

This approval is subject to compliance with the following requirements:

- i. All researchers shall obtain an introduction letter to NACOSTI from the relevant head of institutions (Institute of postgraduate, School dean or Directorate of research)
- ii. The researcher shall further obtain a RESEARCH PERMIT from NACOSTI before commencement of data collection & submit a copy of the permit to **KUREC**.
- iii. Only approved documents including (informed consents, study instruments, MTA Material Transfer Agreement) will be used
- iv. All changes including (amendments, deviations, and violations) are submitted for review and approval by **KUREC**:
- v. Death and life-threatening problems and serious adverse events or unexpected adverse events whether related or unrelated to the study must be reported to **KUREC** within 72 hours of notification;
- vi. Any changes, anticipated or otherwise that may increase the risk(s) or affected safety or welfare of study participants and others or affect the integrity of the research must be reported to **KUREC** within 72 hours;
- vii. Clearance for export of biological specimens must be obtained from relevant institutions and submit a copy of the permit to **KUREC**;
- viii. Submission of a request for renewal of approval at least 60 days prior to expiry of the approval period. Attach a comprehensive progress report to support the renewal and;
- ix. Submission of an executive summary report within 90 days upon completion of the study to **KUREC**

Sincerely,

Prof. Jackson Kitetu PhD
KUREC-Chairman

Cc Vice Chancellor
DVC-Academic & Research
Registrar-Academic & Research
Director-Research Innovation & Outreach
Institute of Post Graduate Studies

As members of Kabarak family, we purpose at all times and in all places, to set apart in one's heart, Jesus as Lord.
(1 Peter 3:15)

Kabarak University is ISO 9001:2015 Certified

Figure 19: KUREC Approval